

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING PHYSICS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS USING INNOVATIVE METHODS

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Abstract. *This article reveals the relevance of using innovative methods of teaching physics in secondary education in Uzbekistan, especially in the context of the modern development of science and technology. The article, based on theoretical and practical aspects, considers the importance of using the principles of teaching physics in this age group. During the study, methods of innovative teaching physics were developed and described, aimed at forming students' ideas about the modern scientific picture of the world. The article analyzes the results of pedagogical experiments, which show that innovative teaching of physics significantly increases students' interest in science, contributes to the development of their creative thinking and potential. Specific examples of methods and tools that can be used to create an attractive and effective learning environment are considered. Thus, the article can become the basis for developing new methods and approaches to teaching physics in secondary schools, as well as for improving the effectiveness of existing methods. It can also become an important contribution to the development of the scientific and creative potential of students and ensuring their successful adaptation in the modern world of science and technology.*

Key words: *physics, secondary education, innovative methods, development.*

Introduction

The current state of society has set the task of restructuring general education into a system of continuous education. This task involves developing the creative potential of students, which should lead to the modernization of the existing traditional education system. Scientists have found that a student with high creative potential differs from others in that: - he/she has creative and intellectual initiative, an active life position; - he/she is able to generate new original ideas when solving problematic issues; - he/she can go beyond the templates and think openly, resolve conflicts that have arisen; - he/she is able to imagine ideas in his/her mind, as well as design the future result of his/her activities; - a creative student has an original way out of a problem situation that has arisen in the educational process; - a creative person is characterized by a constant research need, which allows him/her to be in a state of constant search for the previously unknown (Runko and Jeger, 2012).

Research by scientists has identified creative qualities as an integral characteristic of a person, which include imagination, a sense of novelty, originality of thinking, intuition, fantasy, invention, fine art, logical thinking, etc. (Kaufman and Beghetto, 2009). To develop the creative potential of students, it is necessary to develop a special innovative technology, which is the subject of this article. It should be noted that there are empirical prerequisites for the development of students' creative potential. Pedagogical systems have evolved over time, and such outstanding figures as Comenius (2012) and Pestalozzi (2012) have contributed to early education. Later, educational approaches were developed and improved by psychologists and educators such as Piaget and Inhelder (1972), Bruner (1976) and Montessori (2007). The study analyzed the works of various scientists on the topic of the article and revealed the essence of the

concepts of "creativity" and "creative potential". At the same time, we consider creative potential to be a broader concept than creativity, supplementing its essence with such criteria as "sensitivity to the problem", "ability to analyze and synthesize, to create missing details of the object being studied", "divergent thinking". To achieve the goal of developing the creative potential of students and testing the effectiveness of innovative learning, it was necessary to organize experimental learning. According to Hayes (2006), secondary education is aimed at developing the basics of literacy, knowledge and skills necessary for obtaining general secondary education. Because the goal of general secondary education is to equip students with systemic knowledge of the basics of science, skills and abilities necessary for activities in various areas of the economy, culture and life, as well as for obtaining specialized education, it is of great importance in preparation for further education (Grigg, 2016). That is why it is necessary to consider in more depth the issues of introducing physical concepts from the very first stages of school education.

The aim of the study was to establish the effectiveness of the implementation of innovative teaching methods in physics lessons. To check the possibilities of increasing cognitive independence and creativity, improving the quality of assimilation of physical knowledge of students based on innovative teaching. The presented results of psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature served as the basis for putting forward the idea of the study.

Research questions

1. Is it possible to substantiate the relevance of the problem of applying an innovative approach in teaching physics based on an experiment?
2. Does the use of innovative methods contribute to the achievement of a higher level in teaching physical concepts to school students?
3. What structure of innovative methods in physics ensures not only the achievement of high results in teaching students, but also the development of their personal growth?
4. How effective is the proposed method for applying the developed complex?
5. Is it possible to experimentally test and show the impact of the use of these tools on the formation of interest in science, the development of cognitive independence of students and the improvement of their knowledge in physics?

Methodology

To answer the research questions, a quantitative research method was chosen. Pedagogical experiments were conducted among students and teachers at Secondary School No. 10 in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. At the first stage of the experiment, grade 8 "A" was selected as the experimental group among middle classes, and grade 8 "B" was selected as the control class. The experiments were conducted from September 2021 to March 2022 in three stages: 1 - ascertaining, 2 - main search and 3 - final pedagogical experiment.

Stage 1. The ascertaining experiment at the first stage revealed the main problems of teaching physics. It was found that the existing methods did not meet modern didactic requirements. From conversations with educators and teachers, it was revealed that new methods of teaching physics are needed. At the second stage of the ascertaining experiment, a teaching model was created. The ascertaining experiment at this stage consisted in identifying the main problems of the effectiveness of teaching physics using innovative methods: explaining physical phenomena that can arouse the interest of secondary school students in science; organizing the preparation of relevant trainings for teachers. At this stage, the analysis of the state of education began based on a questionnaire with "teachers and students", their questionnaire and the study of

pedagogical experience.

Stage 2. In order to test and identify the effectiveness of innovative methods and their application in teaching physics, it was necessary to organize and conduct a corresponding pedagogical experiment. The purpose of this experiment was to study the factor on the object of study. Cognitive interest and, therefore, the development of cognitive independence of students is an important reason for improvement and at the same time an indicator of the effectiveness and efficiency of the learning process.

Data on the levels of cognitive independence of students were used as an output variable. The achievement of three levels of cognitive independence by students was considered: reproductive, partially search and research, psychological and didactic aspects of achieving levels of cognitive independence were summarized.

Stage 3. The educational experiment consisted of conducting lessons using innovative methods in physics in a secondary comprehensive school, called experimental. A comparison was made with classes where teaching was conducted without the use of innovative teaching methods. When conducting the experiment, the requirement of representativeness was considered when selecting experimental and control classes in order to avoid unreliability of the results of the pedagogical experiment. Since the improvement of the quality of classes and creative development of students occurs not only from the use of new methods and techniques of teaching, but also from a significant number of other factors, the relationship should not be a functional dependence, but a correlation dependence. To assess these parameters, a null hypothesis is used, which assumes that the observed changes in properties do not depend on the action of an organized parameter, but are determined by secondary, unregulated random causes in the educational process.

There are many new teaching methods in innovative, playful and interactive forms that can be used in secondary schools. Below we present innovative methods, ways of transmitting physics concepts in creative, playful and interactive forms of teaching that we have applied in school institutions.

Table 1. Innovative teaching of physics to students in secondary schools

№	Name of innovative methods and learning technologies
1	Reflection method
2	"Leader-Follower" method
3	Rotation method
4	Analysis of "backlogs"
5	Case technology
6	Problem-based learning technology
7	Facts method
8	Training

Hypothesis. As a null hypothesis H_0 , we put forward the assumption that the development of cognitive independence did not increase after the experiment, there was no correction of knowledge, skills and abilities. Let us form the opposite hypothesis H_1 : the application of innovative methods of teaching physics in secondary education contributes to the development of creative potential. During hypothesis testing, we will decide which of the statements is true in the light of empirical evidence. Let us take the probability of erroneous

rejection of the hypothesis - the level of significance with the usual value of $p = 0,05$. We extract the sample and for the obtained empirical data we determine the statistical criterion and determine the probability of which of their hypotheses is correct. Correlation coefficient, plotting will be obtained using the STATISTICA system. The STATISTICA system is an integrated system for statistical analysis and data processing. Data in STATISTICA is entered in the form of a table, the correlation coefficient r is calculated automatically.

Results

Search experiment results

The achievement by students of three levels of cognitive independence was considered: reproductive, partially exploration and research, psychological and didactic aspects of achieving levels of cognitive independence are summarized in the table.

Table 6. Psychological and didactic aspects of the formation of cognitive independence

Ability Development	Level characteristic	Level
Development of copying ability	It is characterized by the student's desire to understand, remember and reproduce knowledge, to master the way of its application according to the model. The criterion for this level of activity is the desire of students to understand the phenomenon under study.	Reproductive
Reproducing creative activity	It is characterized by the student's desire to reveal the meaning of the content being studied, to penetrate the essence of the phenomenon, to know the connection between phenomena and processes, to master the ways of applying knowledge in changed conditions.	Partial search
Development of the ability of constructive and creative activity	It is characterized not only by interest and desire to penetrate deeply into the essence of phenomena and their relationships, but also by finding a new way.	Research

In accordance with the main ideas of the study, we set tasks, the solution of which was to confirm the correctness of the hypothesis put forward. Thus, based on the results of the test questions, the assumption was finally confirmed that the use of innovative methods in teaching contributes to achieving a higher level of development of cognitive independence. At the search stage of the experiment, didactic tasks of physics teaching aids were determined.

	1 EXP1	2 CONT2	3 VAR3	4 VAR4	5 VAR5
ban1	89,000	37,000			
ban2	89,000	38,000			
ban3	98,000	53,000			
ban4	99,000	53,000			
ban5	89,000	55,000			
ban6	87,000	52,000			
ban7	77,000	52,000			
ban8	77,000	52,000			
ban9	77,000	46,000			
ban10	77,000	54,000			
ban11	91,000	52,000			
ban12	92,000	50,000			
ban13	79,000	45,000			
ban14	79,000	45,000			
ban15	99,000	28,000			
ban16	99,000	28,000			

Figure 2. Data entry into the integrated system of statistical analysis

Figure 3. Correlation calculation

For these schools, a chart of the results of the average grades for the two groups was constructed. On the results diagram, built in three dimensions, two areas of correlation were clearly distinguished. The same result can be seen in the more well-known two-dimensional diagrams. The correlation coefficient $r = -0,37$, which for $p < 0,05$ indicates that there is a moderate relationship. A more visual representation of the correlation can be obtained by analyzing graphs of the dependences of the control and experimental groups relative to each other.

Thus, the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Consequently, the distribution of the results of performing diagnostic tests after the application of innovative teaching methods in the system of continuous education is statistically significant. The analysis of this experiment confirms our hypothesis with a certainty of at least 95% that the use of innovative teaching methods improves the quality of knowledge, this is not due to random factors but has a natural character.

Figure 4. Graphical representation of the dependences of the experimental and control groups with correlation calculation

Results of the training experiment

Comparison of the results of the element-by-element analysis of the tests of the experimental and the averaged results of the control classes leads to the following conclusions:

the average percentage of completing tasks in terms of complexity is the same for the experimental and control classes, that is, the general trends in completing tasks are the same, but the level of completion of all tasks in the experimental class is higher. Further, we can see this in the following figures, which show the results of the tasks, before and after the experiment, among the experimental and control groups.

Figure 5. The average assessment of the performance of tasks in the experimental and control classes of school №10

According to the results of the experiment, it can be seen that the quality of knowledge and the level of assimilation are higher in the experimental grade 8 "A", and the average score for completing tasks is 4.7 points, on a 5-point scale. While the average score for completing tasks in the control grade 8 "B" is 4 points.

Discussion

Analysis of the results of the pedagogical experiment as a whole confirms the hypothesis with a confidence of at least 95% about the existence of a connection between the use of innovative methods and an increase in the quality of knowledge, the achievement of a research level of cognitive independence. The effectiveness of the methodology for using the developed set of tools was experimentally verified and the influence of the use of these tools on the formation of interest in science, the development of cognitive independence of students and an increase in the quality of knowledge in physics was shown.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study presented in this article highlights the importance of using innovative methods of teaching physics in secondary education in Uzbekistan. The article discusses the theoretical and practical aspects of creative teaching of physics and presents various methods and principles that can be used to make learning more effective and enjoyable for students. The results of pedagogical experiments conducted as part of the study demonstrate that innovative teaching of physics can significantly increase students' interest in science and contribute to the development of their creative thinking and potential. This study has important implications for the development of new and improved methods of teaching physics in secondary education, and for promoting the scientific and creative potential of students in Uzbekistan.

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